

ZDZW

ZDZW SOLUTIONS CATALOGUE

The ZDZW project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101057404.

About ZDZW

ZDZW develops **digital non-destructive inspection (NDI) services** as a set of strategic technologies to improve production efficiency, zero-defect, and sustainable manufacturing of European industries.

To pursue the main goal of reducing defects and the generated waste in manufacturing processes, ZDZW addresses defect minimisation and waste reduction in three key areas that cover the entire manufacturing process and product lifecycle.

ZDZW will demonstrate its zero-defect (ZD) and zero-waste (ZW) approach in 6 Pilots involving production processes with an important waste reduction potential like, injection moulding, thermoforming, welding and painting, induction hardening, lithography and packaging.

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Integrity Inspection Suite

Monitor and control key processes like induction hardening, ensure internal component integrity with acoustic emission-based inspections, detect sub-surface defects using MIR-OCT, and automate the inspection of critical welded joints. Experience precision, innovation, and efficiency redefined for the future of manufacturing.

**MECHANICAL
HARDNESS
INSPECTOR**

**AE - BASED
INTEGRITY
ASSESSMENT**

MIR-OCT

EMAT UT

MECHANICAL HARDNESS INSPECTOR

Reduces material waste to 1% and energy consumption by approximately 25%

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

The Mechanical Hardness Inspector offers an innovative inspection solution utilizing **digital twin technology to delineate microstructural and hardness evolution during induction heat treatments.**

Through the utilization of digital twins and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), the production process becomes digitized, enabling **real-time monitoring and analysis.** This integration facilitates **quicker analysis** and **informed decision-making**, thereby **amplifying production efficiency.**

This inspection, powered by digital twin, serves as a valuable tool for industrial partners implementing **induction heat treatments.**

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Automatic unitary inspection
- ▶ Automatic in-depth hardness estimation
- ▶ Early process failures detection
- ▶ Real-time non-destructive inspection

PRODUCT OWNER:

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AE - BASED INTEGRITY ASSESSMENT

Condition monitoring for rotating machinery detecting early-stage damage in industrial components using AE signal analysis

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

This solution **predicts the quality of the product and anticipates possible defects** arising during its manufacturing process by means of Acoustic Emissions (AE).

It integrates **AI tools and data analytics** services to establish quality control techniques, facilitating the inference of correlations among diverse signal parameters, such as signal amplitude, duration, counts, energy, and rise-time, among others.

It allows operators to **stop the production and adjust the manufacturing** process thus avoiding the discard of a whole batch of difficult to reprocess material.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Avoids the discarding of whole batches
- ▶ Detects defects in an early stage
- ▶ NDT in-situ hardness estimation
- ▶ Automates martensite estimation
- ▶ Data-based martensite estimation (no experience needed)

PRODUCT OWNERS:

MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

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EMAT UT

Reduces scrap production by approximately 60%, minimises rework times and improves process yield based on a better defect detection and characterisation

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

Ultrasonic-based system for in-line multi-pass **weld inspection** with defect characterization.

This EMAT UT system caters to the **windmill tower manufacturing industry**, specifically targeting **metal parts manufacturing companies** employing multi-pass welding processes.

Designed to operate at high-temperature environments, this system conducts **real-time in-line inspections**, enabling swift characterization of defects. In comparison to conventional methods, this system offers rapid defect characterization, thereby optimizing efficiency and minimizing production-related setbacks.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Improve on defect characterization (type and size)
- ▶ Reduce scrap production
- ▶ Compare the production statistical analysis with other plants
- ▶ Reduced re-work time

PRODUCT OWNER:

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MIR-OCT

Real-time, non-contact, and non-destructive inspection of ceramic parts with ultra-high-resolution images, significantly reducing defect-related delays and energy waste

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

MIR-OCT introduces an in-line, non-contact, and non-destructive **optical sub-surface inspection technology**. This innovative tool caters to companies involved in **additive ceramic manufacturing equipment** and those requiring **sub-surface inspection of coatings**.

In contrast to the utilization of traditional microscope-based post-manufacturing inspection methods, MIR-OCT **provides real-time fault detection**, leading to streamlined manufacturing processes and reduced waste.

By incorporating this technology, companies can notably **elevate the productivity of zero-defect components while concurrently minimizing energy consumption**.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Sample-dependent, requiring a combination of relatively low optical loss and scattering
- ▶ Fast, efficient, reliable and not dependent on an operator for defect detection and AI algorithm for part quality inspection
- ▶ Optical fault detection and minimisation of delays in delivery of zero-defect products to the customer
- ▶ Easy optimization of manufacturing parameters and reducing energy/manufacturing waste
- ▶ Information can be forwarded to the operator in real time

Visual Inspection Suite

Ensure thorough defect detection in every part introducing cutting-edge techniques like multi-camera 3D scanning and artificial vision. Overcoming limitations, the services prioritize accessibility, providing easily comprehensible defect location information. Elevate manufacturing efficiency with our precise and streamlined visual inspection solutions.

**VOLUMETRIC
INSPECTOR**

**SURFACE
ANOMALY
DETECTOR**

**ARTIFICIAL
VISION**

**AR ENHANCED
INSPECTOR**

VOLUMETRIC INSPECTOR

Analyzes 120 parts per minute, detects 95% of defects, classifies parts by model, and rejects unknown components

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

This solution employs diverse quality analysis techniques to **assess products against expected 3D shapes, identifying deviations and potential defects that could impact final product quality.** Utilizing AI tools, the system learns the anticipated shape and geometric tolerance measurements.

This solution, developed to work in the production line, not only scrutinizes and confirms dimensions but also **identifies geometric flaws such as tears and dents.** Employing an in-line camera-based inspection approach, it **prevents defective pieces from being integrated into the final product.** This proactive measure significantly reduces waste and minimizes energy consumption during production.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Captures images in real time without requiring reconfiguration
- ▶ Measures and detect trends error before they appear
- ▶ Cost reduction: no down-time and no maintenance
- ▶ The inspection system is not subject to human error
- ▶ Part classification, avoiding product specific solutions

SUCCESS STORIES

Manufacturers in the **automotive sector** encountered several challenges:

- The standard process involved sampling only 20% of production.
- They relied on manual processes for assessing complex measurements, impacting precision and accuracy assurance.
- Measure deviation issues arose due to miscalibration of manufacturing machines.

The Volumetric Inspection Solution effectively tackles these challenges by achieving the following objectives:

- Implementing an **inline process for inspecting the entire production**, eliminating the need for sampling.
- **Predicting measure deviation** problems by analyzing trending KPIs.

PRODUCT OWNERS:

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SURFACE ANOMALY DETECTOR

Analyzing 120 parts per minute, detecting 90% of defects, classifying parts by model, and rejecting unknown components

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

The Surface Anomaly Detector employs a 3D camera-based inspection system alongside AI algorithms to assist manufacturers in ensuring comprehensive quality across their entire production line. It effectively **identifies visual defects on the surface of manufactured goods, thereby preventing the inclusion of faulty pieces in the final product.**

The system's focus on detecting surface defects, often challenging to identify through volumetric analysis, is complemented by AI-driven algorithms. These algorithms are trained to analyze images and pinpoint abnormal zones in the object, facilitating efficient defect identification.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Live monitoring of all production parts
- ▶ Part classification, avoiding product specific solutions
- ▶ Cost reduction: no down-time and no maintenance
- ▶ Millimetrical surface defects that human eye cannot detect

SURFACE ANOMALY DETECTOR

Analyzing **120 parts per minute**, detecting **90% of defects**, classifying parts by model, and rejecting unknown components

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MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Live monitoring of all production parts
- ▶ Part classification, avoiding product specific solutions
- ▶ Cost reduction: no down-time and no maintenance
- ▶ Millimetrical surface defects that human eye cannot detect

SUCCESS STORIES

The **bottle stoppers manufacturers** encountered challenges:

- Hundreds of references required human visual inspection.
- Millimeter-level surface defects went undetected, resulting in flawed products reaching clients.

The Surface Anomaly Detector solution effectively resolves these issues by achieving specific objectives:

- Classification of references and algorithm training tailored for each stopper/product.
- High-precision detection of surface defects, preventing customer returns due to product flaws.

PRODUCT OWNERS:

UNIVERSITAT
POLITÈCNICA
DE VALÈNCIA

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ARTIFICIAL VISION

Reducing costs, standardising defect detection and maintaining between 90-99% of human capacity, but guaranteeing inspection stability over time

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

The Edge AI machine vision inspection device is an advanced system **designed for rapid identification of visual defects in manufacturing processes**. It ensures correct assembly and **mitigates the inclusion of faulty components in the final product**.

Tailored for industries such as **aerospace mechanical components, high-precision manufacturing, steelmaking plants, injection plastic parts, and hollow glass manufacturing**, this cutting-edge technology guarantees stringent quality checks for product surfaces.

It integrates a robust image analysis platform with AI techniques into a GPU-based edge device. Suited for manufacturers seeking **comprehensive quality assurance** throughout their production lines, it incorporates image acquisition and analysis devices at the edge, coupled with cloud services for image classification, annotation, and AI model training.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Efficient waste reduction, minimizing scrap, and optimizing energy consumption
- ▶ 100% automatic inspection for inline identification of defects in production, allowing rejection or repairment
- ▶ Easy integration in plant automation and management systems
- ▶ Flexibility and accuracy of AI technology

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METRICS SAMPLES

Hollow glass producers:

- Up to 180 containers/minute
- Defects and anomaly identification on glass surfaces

Aerospace mechanical parts of large surfaces:

- Up to 70x70 mm surface area per second
- Defects and anomaly identification on mechanical components

Identification of cracks on **concrete in building operations**:

- Classification without the need of labeled data
- Automatic segmentation of concrete defects

PRODUCT OWNER:

AR ENHANCED INSPECTOR

Fully automated inspection of wind turbine towers for painting defects in production, providing defect-detection of over 95%

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

The AR-Enhanced Inspector facilitates the **identification and visualization of painting defects on wind turbine towers** through augmented reality, utilizing a handheld device. Its functionality encompasses initial accurate defect detection via a fully automated computer vision system.

The system **aids workers in effectively addressing detected defects by guiding them through navigational overlays**, enhancing their real-world environment. For seamless traceability of the repair process, workers can document repair activities by capturing pictures and adding textual or graphical annotations.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Makes inspection less error-prone, as machines are more reliable than humans
- ▶ Makes the repair-process traceable by allowing easy documentation and annotation
- ▶ Makes fixing defects more precise, by reliably guiding workers to defect locations via augmented reality
- ▶ Saves time for workers, as they can quickly locate defects

PRODUCT OWNERS:

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Thermal Inspection Suite

Obtain real-time quality control for thermoforming, sealing, and welding. Through in-line monitoring and control via Digital Twins and top-tier AI algorithms, these solutions minimise process variability, offering a streamlined approach to thermal manufacturing quality. Benefit from immediate defect detection and eliminate complexities in reworking defective parts.

**WELDING
PROCESS
MONITORING**

**HEAT TRANSFER
DIGITAL TWIN**

**IR THERMAL
INSPECTION**

WELDING PROCESS MONITORING

Online welding defect detector, enabling early detection of potential flaws during welding operations, leading to significant time and material savings

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

This solution caters specifically to **welding SMEs** with a notable expertise in automation but a moderate level of digitalization. It aids SMEs in monitoring their systems and leveraging advanced data analysis techniques for effective data modeling. This facilitates the **creation of an online defect detection system, alerting users to possible defects during welding processes.**

For this solution, a software and hardware system are installed within welding facilities to gather real-time data from the welding process. In the subsequent stage, the collected dataset undergoes analysis and correlation with Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) information. This analysis aids in the **creation of predictive models for online defect identification.**

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Enables an early actuation on defect correction, reducing waste on reworking time and scrap
- ▶ Easy to add new sensor and communication protocols
- ▶ Offers a powerful tool to analyze the real welding process
- ▶ Can be adapted to different welding processes

PRODUCT OWNERS:

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HEAT TRANSFER DIGITAL TWIN

Reduces the defect on thermoforming process up to 50%, reduces the material consumption at least 5% and increases the OEE by around 10%

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

This Thermoforming Digital Twin (SaaS) specifically caters to **appliances and automotive companies**, going beyond mere monitoring solutions available in the market. It **prevents scrap generation and optimizes plastic thickness and energy consumption**, ensuring enhanced efficiency in production.

This advanced digital twin simulates both thermal effects and material deflection caused by thermomechanical loads. It utilizes temperature measurements to calibrate heating elements, employing radiative heat transfer formulations for precise adjustments.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Helps thermoformed plastic part manufacturers to reduce raw material & energy consumptions thanks to its optimization algorithm and defect prevention capability
- ▶ Reduces the thickness, scrap and cost
- ▶ Reduced cycle time
- ▶ Increased throughput

PRODUCT OWNER:

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IR THERMAL INSPECTION

Real-time thermal imaging to monitor the thermoforming and heat-sealing processes in the production line

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

The IR Thermal Imaging Inspection solution serves two distinct applications:

1. **Thermoforming App:** It monitors thermal images of heated and formed plastic sheets during the thermoforming process. This edge-based solution incorporates closed-loop communication control with a digital twin, offering real-time thermal data monitoring in 2D/3D and quality control of produced plastic sheets.

It is **oriented to industries involved in plastic thermoforming**. This solution caters to home appliance manufacturers, automotive manufacturers, and similar sectors engaged in thermoforming processes.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Monitors thermal images and detect the defects in real time.
- ▶ Generates 2D/3D thermal profile of the produced plastic parts.
- ▶ Edge-based system, detecting defects in thermal imaging that might not be visually discernible.

Thermal Profile Analysis Page

PRODUCT OWNERS:

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IR THERMAL INSPECTION

Real-time thermal imaging to monitor the thermoforming and heat-sealing processes in the production line

SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

The IR Thermal Imaging Inspection solution serves two distinct applications:

2. **Heat Sealing Process App:** It oversees the filling and sealing process of all products through non-intrusive inline inspection. It provides real-time 4D data, enabling comprehensive monitoring and control of every step within the heat-sealing process.

This solution serves industries involved in heat-sealing or induction sealing of various packaging types, including capsules, bottles, flow packs, and others.

MAIN BENEFITS

- ▶ Allows preventive maintenance for good process sequence.
- ▶ Real-time about bad process trends.
- ▶ Accurate system, detecting defects in thermal imaging, which may not be visually evident.

Main screen of IRTI for Heat-sealing

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Meet the partners

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